

SOCIOPRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF COMMUNICATION
(based on the story “Ta’ziya” by Erkin A’zam)

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Annotation: In this article, the story “Ta’ziya” written by Erkin A’zam is analysed from a sociopragmatic point of view. In this context, the principles of sociopragmatic analysis and theoretical information about its role in understanding the work of art are presented with the help of specific examples.

Keywords: Sociopragmatic analysis, text, communication, adresant, adresat.

As language develops as a result of the development of society, the influence of the social environment on language and the form of its manifestation – speech – is very great. The nature of the environment in which a person lives is clearly reflected in his speech. People’s way of living, work, study, conditions, and environmental changes are also reflected in his speech. The issue of the influence of the social environment on language is the focus of sociolinguistic research.

When analysing a work of art, it is impossible not to connect it with social life. To understand the work of art, to understand its idea, to listen to the writer’s ideas that he wants to convey to the reader through the work, the reader must have a certain level of knowledge about the social environment described in the work, the period in which the heroes of the work lived, and the socio-political system to which they belong.

As noted by I.A. Goncharov, “Language is not only speaking, speech: language is the whole inner world of a person: his mind, heart, representative of all mental and moral forces” [3, 67]. People communicate based on cultural norms in mutual relations. Where there are no standards, there is no culture, and rudeness and rudeness are reflected in the expression of words.

The sociopragmatic analysis of the text is an important step in entering the simulated situation. This analysis is carried out according to the following parameters:

- 1) Determining the form of communication;
- 2) Determination of communication status;
- 3) Determine the characteristics of the adresat;
- 4) to determine the unique characteristics of the adresant [2, 9].

Based on the above, we will try to sociopragmatically analyse Erkin A’zam’s story “Ta’ziya”.

The play “What if a ball is not found in the house of an Uzbek!” begins with a sentence. This means that Uzbek men have been wearing hats since ancient times, and every household must have a hat. However, some of the events described in the work took place during the colonial period, and this period was a time when efforts to destroy Uzbek culture and traditions intensified. This is also confirmed by the following sentence in the speech of the heroes of the work: “The tradition left by our ancestors, ulim. Once upon a time, it was brave to wear it. We have seen a lot of people who are thirsty, saying, Why don’t you wear a hat, why are you ashamed? We know your purpose”. At that time, wearing a headdress and performing funeral prayers were considered old fashioned and prohibited.

One of the main characters of the work is Salim Safarov (Salim Qaror – he became Salim Qaror because he wrote the decisions of the meeting in the Shuroda with admiration). Let's pay attention to the conversation about Salim Qaror between the heroes of the play, father and son:

– Doomsday was a man, – I said, remembering Salim Qaror.

– Doomsday! – said my father dreamily, while reversing the car. – “I was born on the seventh of November of the seventeenth year – on the day of the revolution, I am the same age as October, and originally my horse should have been either October or Revolution”. – Then, as if drunk, my father continued talking: – I'm sorry, I'm ten years younger than you, and I don't know exactly what year and month I was born, did you ask your mother?!

– Belief, father, dogmatic belief.

– Yes, I saw the power of the faith you mentioned in this person. He believed in the printed word. If you printed on a piece of paper and wrote “Your brother is against the government's policy”, he would not hesitate to run to his younger brother with a cane. From then on, there was no mansabi left that did not ride on this roll. He worked in the executive committee of the district, first he became the chairperson of the collective farm, then the council, he was a farmer, and he was a member of the militia. Well, there is no more. This is the end – journalism. However, it is necessary to say what was said in the servant's office: he did so many deeds and betrayed neither the state nor the people. If not, what difficult years it was! During the postwar famine, when his uncle went crying, “My children are starving”, he knocked on the door of the barn and said, “There is no wheat, it belongs to the state!” They say he returned it dry. Such was the man who was given. You don't know modern architecture. For many years, his son was not circumcised. True or false, there is also a rumour that his mother-in-law was buried without a funeral. I can't say for sure – I was studying in Tashkent. Look at the firmness of faith! He only graduated from the course of literacy. However, whether you say “Capital” or the politics of the time, he would close his eyes and tell. All from independent reading and enthusiasm! “I have been a Marxist since I was fourteen years old”, he used to say. He died.

“Marxists are also dying”, I simply said, depending on the tone of the conversation.

– Everyone will die. However, in your own language, “their bright memory will remain forever in hearts”, right?

I couldn't keep silent at this statement mixed with sarcasm (“Ta'ziya”).

It is clear from Salim Qaror's “firm belief in the printed letter” that he always worked loyally to the government in whatever position he worked throughout his life, he lived in fear of opposing the political system or making a political mistake, which is why there is no career horse left in this pack that he has not ridden. In the years of famine, he does not give wheat to his uncle and does not betray government property. He strictly obeyed the system of that time, fulfilled the tasks unconditionally, and gave up his personal interests along the way; there are times when he is even forced to give up his faith. We can see the proof of this in “Many years his son was not circumcised. Whether it's true or not, there is also a saying that his mother-in-law was buried without a funeral”.

Salim Qaror uses force for trivial reasons and gets punished by the systems. For this reason, extreme caution is evident in every move he makes:

– Father, we described this man as religious. I think he was just plain cowardly.

– There is soul in what you say, my son, – said my father. – It is true that during Stalin's time, he lost his heart. They tortured him by wrapping him in felt for a week in the Termiz

prison. There is a torture method called “Felt Punishment”. I heard from his own mouth. During the kolkhoz period, he lay down in the threshing floor one night and wept drunkenly. Do you know what they accused him of? For rhyming “betayin” with “Stalin”. Salim Qaror was a poet, what a poet! He used to write ghazals and then sing them. We have heard. We were children in it.

Salim Qaror’s “We used to write when we were young. Then, I couldn’t get the rhyme right...” I remembered his dreamy words. That’s the point.

– Maybe then, when they were tortured, he couldn’t bear it and took up espionage? It was as if Grandfather was up to something.

– There may be, my son. If he had a secret, he took it with him (“Ta’ziya”).

As we know from history, Stalin was a member of the editorial board of the Pravda newspaper in 1917, the Politburo of the Central Committee of the RSDRP (b) and the Military-Revolutionary Center. In 1917-1922, People’s Commissar for National Affairs, in 1919-1922, People’s Commissar of State Control, since 1918, a member of the Military Revolutionary Council of Russia. From 1922 to 1953, he was the General Secretary of the Central Committee of the party. During this period, Salim Qaror was severely punished for rhyming “betayin” to “Stalin” in one of his poems; he stopped writing poems and started doing other things.

After the “Felt Punishment”, he becomes more careful and tries to perform his religious deeds secretly from people:

– Father, you said that he is the one who buried his mother-in-law without a funeral. Was this man praying?

– If he has read it, he has read it, but no one has seen it. He used to take part in funerals and stay aside during funerals. What happened then?

– Well, I don’t remember...

Remember. I used to look after Salim Qaror when he left for the evening duty. If I go out for a short walk around the yard before the printing house prepares the last page, then when I come back – close the door. I pushed harder, and the chain opened with a flash. I see... someone is lying on the ground. My teacher, Salim Qaror! Sensing the ghost, he picked something up from the floor and slammed it under the table. Joynamoz? Then, he got up with a groan, clutching his waist, pressed the paper lying on the table with his palm, pushed it across the floor and put it in his pocket without hesitation. The red thing looks like a document...

– Come on, nephew, the page is not ready yet, – said Salim Qaror in a sinful tone and added with a moan: – Dry back hurts. Let’s take a look at this...

Let him run away! When you pray, don’t you read openly, what’s wrong with me? It turned out that during the day he sent me out to the other room... This is the reason why he doesn’t say anything even if I stay for a long time (“Ta’ziya”).

Later, Salim Qaror lives very cautiously; even if he participates in funeral processions with people, he stays aside during funerals, and he prays hidden from people’s eyes. Later, he does not come to work due to work leave and submits an application through his son and does not come to work.

Our scientists evaluate Salim Qaror as a representative of the “deluded generation”. “In the prose of Erkin A’zam, Bolta Mardon (“Suv yoqalab”), Salom chapdast (“Chapdast”), Pakana artist (“Pakananing oshiq ko’ngli”), Salim Qaror (“Ta’ziya”), Mirzo Ramazon, Farxod Ramazon, Baynalmilalchi Bobo (“Shovqin”), Shuro Bobo, O’rmon kalta (“Guli-guli”), there are hundreds of

characters, many of them are lost in the ideal, and some are lost in both the ideal and the heart. In general, Erkin A'zam tried to perfectly interpret the lives, tragedies, beliefs of the "deceived generation" in crisis, and the suffering of the heroes who live against their wishes. The period of independence in Uzbek prose "The fate of the deluded generation" ("A generation whose life is miserable") has been covered by dozens of our artists from different angles. Therefore, we think that our young researchers should study this literary reality systematically, monographically, with new modern scientific and theoretical views, and make excellent scientific observations" [3, 6-7].

References:

1. Аъзам Э. Танланган асарлар: 1-жилд. Ҳикоялар. – Тошкент: "Sharq" нашриёт-матбаа акциядорлик компанияси бош таҳририяти, 2021. – 544 б.
2. Комарова Ю.А., Гулевич О.М. Использование прагмалингвистического тренажера для формирования иноязычной социопрагматической компетенции у студентов-филологов//Известия ВГПУ. – [Волгоград](#), 2018. №4 (127). – С. 8-12.
3. Комарова Ю.А., Gulevich O.M. The use of a pragmalinguistic simulator for the formation of foreign language sociopragmatic competence among philology students//Izvestiya VGPU. – Volgograd, 2018. No. 4 (127). – P. 8-12.
4. Ёўлдошев Н., Шофиев О. Эркин Аъзам бадий олами. – Тошкент: "Turon zamin ziyo" нашриёти, 2014. – 304 б.
5. Yuldoshev N., Shofiev O. Art world of Erkin A'zam. – Tashkent: "Turon zamin ziyo" publishing house, 2014. – 304 p.
6. Черкашина Т.Т. Язык деловых межкультурных коммуникаций. Учебник. – Москва: ИНФРА-М, 2017. – 368 с.
7. Cherkashina T.T. The language of business intercultural communications. Textbook. – Moscow: INFRA-M, 2017. – 368 p.